

Replication Research: Journal Description

Abstract

In close collaboration with a large community of researchers and FORRT, we have developed materials for the newly established diamond open-access journal: Replication Research (replicationresearch.org). This report was created to enable other researchers and journals to cite, view different versions, and reuse its contents.

About the journal

[Replication Research \(R2\)](#) is co-owned by the [Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training \(FORRT\)](#) and the [Münster Center for Open Science \(MüCOS\)](#). It is hosted by the [University and State Library Münster, University of Münster](#).

Acknowledgments

We thank participants from the “Road to R2” online discussion sessions, contributors from the Replication Research Symposium, members of the R2 Advisory Board, and contributors from our open community call. For a complete list of people who participated in the creation of this journal, please see forrt.org/contributors by searching “replication research”.

Funding

This research was supported by the Landesinitiative openaccess.nrw (<https://osf.io/a82fe>) and the University of Münster Topical Program (<https://osf.io/wqe7n>). We gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by both organizations.

Note on versions

The most recent version of this publication may not perfectly reflect the contents of R2’s current website since we will update this publication only after considerable changes have been made.

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Free to read, free to publish

Replication Research is a Diamond Open Access Journal with strict and entirely transparent quality control and no article processing charges. We publish close and conceptual replications as well as reproductions.

Valuing high-quality replication research and interdisciplinary discussions

Replications, that is the repeated testing of previously published claims, should be the foundation for cumulative and quantitative science but they are not. We are here to change this. If you seek to publish replication research such as reproductions (same data) or replications (different data) with rigorous and transparent quality assurance (open and persistent peer review, reproducibility check) in an open and accessible way, we are here for you.

Due to replication research gaining momentum across fields such as economics, psychology, biostatistics, earth science, humanities, and medicine, new methods to conduct and assess replications are being developed. Currently, researchers work in parallel and thus do double work. *Replication Research* is a place where expertise from different fields comes together in form of theory papers to shape the gold standard for transdisciplinary replication research.

Fields from which *Replication Research* welcomes submissions:

- Digital Humanities
- Experimental Philosophy
- Geoscience
- Linguistics
- Management Sciences
- Marketing
- Medicine
- Mental health

- Metascience
- Neuroimaging
- Neuroscience
- Political Science
- Psychology
- Qualitative Research
- Quantitative Methods/Statistics

Researcher-led

Replication Research is hosted by the University of Münster and maintained by the [Münster Center for Open Science \(MüCOS\)](#) and the [Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training \(FORRT\)](#).

About the Journal

Replication Research is an interdisciplinary journal for replication research. This includes reproductions, where the same code and data are used to verify the originally reported results, close replications, where new data is collected with a method closely resembling an original study, or conceptual replications, where a previously tested hypothesis is re-tested using new methods and new data. For an up-to-date list of disciplines from which we accept submissions, see our [landing page](#). If your discipline is not covered and you would like to submit your research, please get in touch with the Editor-in-Chief.

Diamond Open Access without Processing Fees

Replication Research is a researcher-led journal that is and will forever be free to read and to publish (Diamond Open Access, no Article Processing Charges).

Open and Persistent Peer Review

All reviews are published after each round of peer-review, that is, regardless whether the manuscript is accepted or rejected for publication. Reviews are added as comments on the submitted preprint via [PubPeer](#).

Reproducibility

Before publication, reproducibility checks are conducted for the reported results. Articles are not published unless these reproducibility checks are successful. This process is overseen by the reproducibility manager and conducted by the reproducibility team.

Article Types

Replication Research accepts submissions that include reproducibility checks (including multiverse analyses and many analyst studies), internal

or direct replications, close replications, and conceptual replications as long as the target study is specified and published.

For more information, see the [Submission Guidelines](#).

TOP Guidelines

The following table stems from the [Center for Open Science](#). Replication Research requires level 3 adherence to most Transparency and Openness Promotion (TOP) guidelines. Adherence to *TOP Research Practices* is checked by the editorial assistant and the handling editor. *Verification Practices* are organized by the journal, that is the reproducibility manager. *Replication Research* accepts all types of Verification Studies.

Criterion	Level	Explanation
Study Registration	1	Authors stated whether or not a study was registered—and, if so, where and when it was registered.
Study Protocol	1	Authors stated whether or not the study protocol is available—and, if so, where and when it was shared.
Analysis Plan	3	The editorial assistant certifies that the analysis plan was shared and complete per disciplinary best-practice.
Materials Transparency	3	The editorial assistant certifies that materials were deposited and documented per disciplinary best-practice.
Data Transparency	3	The reproducibility manager certifies that data were deposited with metadata per disciplinary best-practice.
Analytic Code	3	The reproducibility manager certifies that analytic code was deposited and documented per disciplinary best-practice.

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Reporting 3
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The reviewers certify that the authors adhered to the cited reporting guideline.

Verification Practice

Definition

Comprehensive Reporting

The reviewers verify that the study registration, protocol, and analysis plan match the final report—and the final report acknowledges any deviations from these outputs.

Computational Reproducibility

The reproducibility manager certifies that reported results reproduce using shared data and code.

Verification Study Type

Definition

Replication

A study that aims to provide diagnostic evidence about claims from a prior study by repeating the original study procedures in a new sample.

Registered Report

A registered study in which a study protocol and analysis plan are peer reviewed, and the study is pre-accepted by a publication outlet, before the research is undertaken.

Multiverse

A study that tests the research question of interest across multiple datasets arising from different, reasonable choices for processing and analyzing the same data.

Many Analyst

A study in which independent analysis teams conduct plausible alternative analyses of a research question on the same dataset.

Publication Process

Additional Information

ISSN: 3052-5977

Funding: Supported by the Münster Center for Open Science, University of Münster and the *Landesinitiative openaccess.nrw*

Replication Research is a member of [OJSred.net](https://osf.io/p4dzb) and dpjedi.org.

Contributions and References

These guidelines are shared under a CC BY 4.0 and have been created by Lukas Röseler (Writing - first draft) and the Replication Research Consortium (list of members available online, <https://osf.io/p4dzb>). They are loosely based on the submission guidelines from Meta Psychology (<https://open.lnu.se/index.php/metapsychology/about/submissions>).

Editorial Team

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- Prince Oppong Boakye (University of Münster): Reproducibility Manager
- Miriam Müller (University of Münster): Editorial Assistant
- Neele Kolber (University of Münster): Research Intern

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Advisory Board members are invited by the Senior Editors and the EiC. Their tasks include participating in an annual, 90-minute online meeting with the editorial board to discuss journal strategy, offering symbolic support by promoting R2 within their networks, and suggesting potential reviewers or associate editors to improve our editorial workflow. Advisory board members are publicly credited on [FORRT's Contributors](#) page.

Institutional OJS Support

We are grateful to the University of Münster's OJS team, consisting of Stephanie Klötgen, Elisabeth Sawatzky, Jens Unkenholz and Claudia Mohr, for their wonderful support in working with Open Journal Systems.

Guidelines for Editors

- **Handling and Crediting of Additional Comments**

Peer review is open to every researcher who provides comments on the article before the respective deadline. Feedback from external reviewers (in contrast to invited reviewers) may be incorporated into the review letters. In this case, external reviewers will be credited as such as they do not fill out the reviewer disclosure form (see Review Guidelines). In the case of many thorough external reviews, editors should consider issuing an open call for comments on the respective manuscript.

- **Different Standards Between Fields**

Editors acknowledge that methodological and conceptual standards across fields vary. To allow research from fields with less strict standards to be published, too, editors are responsible for the reviews to be framed adequately.

- **Editorial Members' Conflict of Interest**

For the foundation of Replication Research, we gathered experts on replication research from various disciplines. At the same time, replication research is conducted and published only rarely. This might lead to potential conflicts of interests, where members of the editorial team or their close colleagues submit research articles. For this reason, we require reviewers to disclose whether they have been working together with the author / one of the authors or with the handling editor. If an editor is a co-author in a submitted manuscript, they must include a COI statement and a different editor must handle the submission.

Mentorship Program

Our Mentorship Program will start in spring 2026. It engages students and postdocs as volunteers in a variety of journal tasks, offering them valuable editorial experience and academic self-governance skills.

Program Features:

- **Roles:** Depending on their past experience, mentees contribute to typesetting and reprochecks or participate in the editorial workflow as reprocheckers, reviewers, and associate editors.
- **Crediting:** Contributions are transparently acknowledged on our editorial team website and within manuscript metadata.
- **Integration:** The program aligns with [FORRT's Remote Mentorship Program](#), fostering open and reproducible research practices, particularly for underrepresented groups.
- **Community:** Mentees will gain connections with leading Open Science scholars and other mentees through joint trainings.

Application:

If you are interested in the program, please reach out to the Journal Manager (see Contact). For every suitable application, the editorial team will try to find a volunteer mentor with appropriate skills and fitting expertise. Provided that a match can be found, we will put the mentor and mentee in contact with each other.

Constitution

The constitution has been published as a stand-alone item at <https://zenodo.org/communities/r2/records>.

Submissions

Submission Preparation Checklist

As part of the submission process, authors are required to check off their submission's compliance with all of the following items, and submissions may be returned to authors that do not adhere to these guidelines.

- Preprint uploaded to a non-commercial repository (e.g., Zenodo, ArXiv), accessible, and assigned a DOI.
- Cover letter includes preprint DOI, at least two reviewer suggestions, list of badges that the authors apply for (data, code, materials, registration), reference to the reporting guideline(s) used by the authors, and optionally request for Social Responsibility Evaluation and request for results-blind peer review (reproductions only).
- The Preregistration link is accessible and included in manuscript (if the study was preregistered). If the study was not preregistered but contains data analyses, the authors included a statement declaring that it was not preregistered.
- All deviations from the preregistration are disclosed and discussed (if the study was preregistered).
- Data, materials, and code have been made openly available and accessible by linking them in the manuscript. If sharing certain materials is not feasible (e.g., due to ethical, privacy, or legal considerations), authors should clearly state the reasons and, where possible, describe how access requests or alternatives can be handled. Our editorial team is committed to supporting authors in addressing any challenges with data sharing. Please note that if open materials are removed post-publication without valid justification, this may lead to retraction of the article.
- Instructions for reproducibility checks provided and linked in the manuscript.
- All authors agree that in case of acceptance the paper including all corresponding materials will be published under a CC BY 4.0 attribution license by the journal. Bibliographic metadata including abstracts will be published under a CC0 license. Copyright remains with the authors.

- All authors agree with the manuscript's content, the order of the authors, the CRediT statement, and Replication Research's policies.
 - Authors have included a brief subsection 'Social Impact & Responsibility' (see the "SIR" in the constitution for details: <https://www.uni-muenster.de/Ejournals/index.php/replicationresearch/constitution>).
 - Manuscript includes statements on potential conflicts of interests and funding for all contributors.
 - If applicable, an ethics statement from the institutional review board is submitted.
 - The authors confirm that they have the legal right to publish all figures, images, and data included in the manuscript; that all sources and ideas from others are appropriately cited to avoid plagiarism; and that they take full responsibility for any violations of copyright or ethical standards related to their submission.
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Author Guidelines

Replication Research is a peer-reviewed journal for replications and reproductions from various disciplines. Articles need to disclose what original study and hypothesis/claim they replicated or reproduced. For an up-to-date overview of the disciplines from which we accept submissions, please see the editorial board. Generally, we can provide adequate quality assurance and peer review for cognitive, behavioral, and social science studies (psychology, economics, sociology, education sciences, political sciences, management, medicine, life sciences).

Please note that the entire review process is open and reviews will be permanently linked with submitted manuscripts via their DOIs and Pubpeer.com regardless whether the article is accepted or rejected. This is so that quality assurance is transparent, and so that work provided by reviewers for Replication Research is credited and not discarded.

Authors seeking guidance regarding reproduction and replication studies can consult FORRT's handbook for reproduction and replication studies (https://forrt.org/replication_handbook).

- **Pre-Submission checks**

We encourage authors to conduct automated checks before submission. These include checks of reported test statistics and p-values via [statcheck.io](#), checks for non-cited replication studies via [FReD Annotator](#), and checks for cited retracted articles via [Papercheck \(ScienceVerse\)](#).

- **Preprints**

Before submission, articles must be posted to a preprint server that assigns the article a DOI (e.g., [arXiv](#), [OSF preprints](#), [Zenodo](#)).

- **Author Contributions**

Author contributions must be reported using the [Contributor Role Taxonomy \(CRediT\)](#).

- **Preregistration**

We recommend studies to be preregistered and justify exceptions. If applicable, the link to the preregistration must be included in the manuscript and accessible during peer review. Note that secondary data analyses can be preregistered, too. For preregistered studies, the authors must disclose whether the analysis plan was included in the preregistration and whether the analysis script was preregistered, and whether they already had access to the data by the time they preregistered. All deviations from the preregistration must be discussed openly with respect to (1) a description of the deviation, (2) a justification for it, and (3) a note on how the deviation does or might affect the results.

- **Open Data, Materials, and Code**

Data, materials, and code should be posted to a trusted repository (e.g., [osf.io](#), [researchbox.org](#), [zenodo.org](#)). Links to the repository must be included in the manuscript. Upon acceptance, the authors create a frozen version of the repository and update all links (e.g., via [OSF Registrations](#)). Exceptions to this rule must be identified and justified at article submission (e.g., data privacy, ethical reasons). In these cases, authors must add a justification in their report (Closed Data Statement).

- **Transparency Statement**

Authors must declare all potential conflicts of interest, include the [21 word solution](#) (“*We report how we determined our sample size, all data exclusions (if any), all manipulations, and all measures in the study.*”) or a derivative thereof, and explain if and how they are

connected to the authors of the original work. Authors must declare use of AI (e.g., “The introduction has been drafted by ChatGPT 5”). Finally, for empirical submissions, authors should include a file-drawer statement in which they declare that they have reported all studies that they carried out on this topic.

- **Reproducibility**

Results need to be reproducible. That means, the authors need to provide simple instructions on how to reproduce all results reported in the manuscript. To facilitate reproducibility checks, we encourage authors to use free open source software. A link to the instructions needs to be included in the manuscript. Replication Research will conduct reproducibility checks that adhere to the [CODECHECK principles](#).

- **PubPeer commenting**

Regardless of the decision (accept, revise, reject), reviews and responses will be posted to PubPeer (pubpeer.com) after each review stage. They will be prominently labelled as Peer Review Reports to avoid confusion with expressions of concern prevalent on PubPeer.

- **Collaborative Copy-Editing**

Replication Research has no author processing charges. To be able to maintain the journal, authors are expected to engage in copy-editing. Consequently, this phase will take as long as a peer review round. To prevent long publication times, an unformatted “online first” version of the article will be published before the final layout is ready.

Article Types

Articles submitted to *Replication Research* need to investigate a research question that has been previously investigated in a published study or discuss replication methods that are relevant for at least two different research areas. Empirical reports can be computational reproductions using the same data and code, robustness checks using the same data but different procedures, close replications using new data and the same method, or conceptual replications using new data and a different method. Replication closeness needs to be described in detail.

Badges

For articles meeting the requirements listed in the Author Guidelines, we assign the following badges (images provided by [OSF](#) and [CODECHECK](#)):

- Open Materials
- Open Data
- Open Code
- Preregistered
- Code works

Reproductions (same data)

For reproductions (i.e., studies where no new data is collected), we recommend using the Institute for Replication's template available via this [OSF Project](#) or FORRT's Standardized Reproduction Template (StaRT, [long](#) or [short](#) form). We do not accept reproductions with overlapping authorship with the authorship team of the original article. Reproductions should expand the original analyses in some way (e.g., generalizability or robustness checks). Numerical reproductions (e.g., rerunning the code) are not accepted. Authors can propose results-blind peer-review for reproduction studies via an informal request in the submission's cover letter.

Replications (different data)

Replication studies test a previously published claim or hypothesis using different data from the original study. They can be internal (i.e., by the same group of researchers), close, or conceptual (for a typology, see [Hüffmeier et al., 2016](#)). Authors can use their own format or a standardized template provided by Replication Research. This [Standardized Reproduction Template \(StaRT\)](#) is available online at <https://osf.io/3jgxd>. Replication articles should provide subjective author assessment and guideline-based assessment of success (for guidance, see our [Handbook](#)). If possible, authors should also include a reproduction of the original study. We generally recommend reproduction before replication.

Upon acceptance, we expect authors to enter their replication study into the FORRT Replication Database (if it is not included yet; [form](#)).

Multiverse Analyses and Many Analyst Studies

There are many paths from raw data to results. Approaches that aim to explore most or all of these paths and compare how robust a finding is to analytic decisions, among other factors, are called *multiverse* or *specification curve analyses*; Approaches that systematically vary choices regarding analysis, variable and sample selection approaches that involve many people choosing their preferred path of data analysis independently and comparing them are called *Many-Analyst Studies*. Both contain information about robustness or generalizability and are thus an integral part of *repetitive research*.

Multi-study articles

For multi-study articles, a mix of replications and reproductions is possible. Authors need to disclose for each study whether it is a replication or reproduction. A mix of original studies and replication is not possible.

Registered Reports

Replication Research accepts registered reports for studies where new data is collected. More information on registered reports is available in the [guide to registered reports](#).

Replication Reviews

Replication Reviews can be meta-analyses and reviews that focus on replications and reproductions (e.g., to aggregate the state of replicability across a field of literature). For meta-analyses of replications, we recommend including a meta-analysis of the original effects which is being replicated alongside the meta-analysis of replications, and eventually a pooled meta-analysis of both original and replication studies. Replications

or reproductions of meta-analyses should be submitted to the Replications or Reproductions section.

We do not accept articles that estimate replicability across a body of original literature statistically, using methods such as z-curve or p-curve, as they do not constitute repetitive research (i.e., but would be acceptable as part of a larger project). Instead, the focus is on the accumulation of evidence from replication/reproduction studies.

Replication Methods and Perspectives

Theoretical contributions to methods of all types of replication research should be relevant to multiple research areas. These papers may introduce and validate new methods, or discuss the role and limitations of repetitive research in a specific context (e.g., the quality of reproduction studies in undergraduate theses).

Tutorials

Practical introductions to methods or tools relevant for conducting repetitive research.

Comments

Replication Research welcomes comments on articles published in our pages. If several comments make similar points, the editors will select one for review. Authors will be given the opportunity to submit one aggregated Reply to comments.

Copyright Notice

All articles and corresponding materials are published under a [CC BY 4.0](#) license. For special cases involving ethical or legal restrictions, there is the option to provide access to the data only to the journal.

Contributions and References

These guidelines are shared under a CC BY 4.0 and have been created by the members of the R2 editorial board. They are loosely based on the submission guidelines from [Meta Psychology](#) and [Free Neuropathology](#).

Privacy Statement

The names and email addresses entered in this journal site will be used exclusively for the stated purposes of this journal and will not be made available for any other purpose or to any other party.

Reviewer Guidelines

Transparency

To make quality assurance as transparent as possible, reviews need to be signed by the reviewers and they will be published after each round of peer-review by the journal. They will be permanently linked with the submitted preprint through a comment on [PubPeer](#). This is regardless of whether the article is accepted, returned for revision, or rejected.

Reviewers can request pseudonymization before they submit their review. That is, pubpeer comments and the published peer review report will not include the reviewers' name but a pseudonym. The reviewer's name is known to the handling editor, and the senior editors. Reviewers' pseudonyms can be made public by R2 upon request by the respective reviewers.

Disclosures

Reviewers are asked to make a recommendation (accept, revise, reject) and to justify their decision. Reviewers are required to review the manuscript and supplemental materials and need to disclose whether they reviewed the preregistration, materials, data, and code.

Involvement of Original Authors

For reproduction and replication studies, we request reviews from independent researchers and authors of the repeated study. Reviewers must not all be original authors.

Reviewer code of conduct

Reviewers are expected to provide constructive feedback. Personal attacks, coercion to cite their research, or vague criticism may lead to reviewers being blacklisted to review articles for Replication Research. Reviewers must not base their decision on the outcome, that is, acceptance/rejection

due to a successful or failed replication is not considered in the editorial board's decisions.

Reviewers must declare all potential conflicts of interest and explain if and how they are connected to the authors of the original work. Reviewers must declare use of AI (e.g., “Points 2 and 3 are based on the suggestions of ChatGTP 5”).

For reviewers seeking guidance, we recommend [PCI Psychology's guide for reviewers](#).

Review checklist

- Decision (accept, revise, reject)
- Justification / Comments for the authors
- Review coverage (manuscript, original report, supplemental materials, preregistration, materials, data, code, push-button replicability)

Disclosures:

- I recommend a statistical expert to give feedback on the analyses.
- The Social Responsibility Review should be conducted.
- My comments adhere to the [reviewer code of conduct](#) in that they are constructive and targeted at improving the manuscript.
- I have been working together with the author / one of the authors.
- I have been working together with the editor handling this submission.
- In cases where I have suggested the citation of studies that I co-authored, I have disclosed that I am a co-author and justified why this paper and not another one should be cited.

Reproducibility Check

The editorial team, specifically the reproducibility manager, will ensure numerical reproducibility of accepted empirical articles. Authors will

receive instructions for how to share data and code after acceptance of their article.